

Validation of the performance assessment protocol for NH₃ and HCl

Version 1.0

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Title Protocol for the performance evaluation of gas analysers used for biomethane conformity assessment		
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Abstract In order to meet the requirements of biomethane gas quality standards EN 16723-1 and EN 16723-2, reliable and traceable purity analysis of biomethane is required. This report validates the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol (developed in A2.1.4) by demonstrating its applicability hydrogen chloride (HCl) using laser spectroscopy. Further, it also discussed the applicability of the protocol to hydrogen fluoride (HF).		
Key words Biomethane conformity assessment, biomethane, protocol, performance assessment, hydrogen chloride, ammonia, hydrogen fluoride		
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1. Introduction

This report describes the validation of the fitness of purpose of the protocol developed in activity A2.1.4 for the measurement in biomethane using laser spectroscopic techniques operated at VSL. This is done for hydrogen chloride (HCl) as part of activity A2.2.3. In addition, the applicability of the protocol to the validation of measurements of hydrogen fluoride (HF) in biomethane will be described (no experimental work will be carried out for HF).

The EN standard EN16723-1:2016 provides specifications for biomethane for injection in the natural gas network. For chlorinated compounds (as well as for HF), EN16723-1:2016 does not give a clear upper limit. Instead, it refers to CEN/TR 17238:2018 [4], which gives an approach for assessment of limit values of contaminants in biomethane based on health assessment criteria, modelling and different scenarios, and it does not consider other impacts of these contaminants such as on the integrity of pipelines or appliances. As a result, the limit value for chlorinated compounds is both country-dependent (as health criteria values are typically determined at the national level) and application-specific. Accordingly, corresponding limit values for HCl do vary over a wide range, ranging from a few mg m^{-3} to values exceeding several hundred mg m^{-3} (note 1 mg m^{-3} is approximately $0.67 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ at standard reference conditions).

Here we chose to validate the HCl analyzer at the more challenging range of the lower $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ down to sub $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$. Higher amount fractions could be relatively easily measured with the set-up using either dynamic dilution or choosing a measurement cell with a shorter optical path length.

2. Scope of the validation

The extent of the performance characteristic validation for HCl and NH_3 analyzers in biomethane is summarized in Table 1. Here not a full validation has been performed as, in particular for selectivity when one could test all kinds of different matrix compositions which would require very extensive experiments beyond the budget of this project. However, the results described here will provide some insights into how a full validation can be performed.

Table 1 *Extent of validation for HCl analyzers in biomethane. Note that for selectivity only very limited experiments were carried out. A full test would require a test with a much wider range of potential interfering compounds. As both analyzers can be used for on-line analysis, here also the response time is included in the validation.*

Performance characteristic	Component quantification
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Selectivity (only for NH ₃)	x
Limit of detection	
Limit of quantification	x
Working range	x
Precision	x
Response time	x

3. Analytical methods and reference gas standards

a. HCl analyzer

The custom-built TDLs spectrometer employs an interband cascade laser (Nanoplus, Germany) with collimator. The laser is used to probe the P6 line of HCl centred at 3633.68 nm (2752.04 cm⁻¹) which has a line strength of $S=1.92 \cdot 10^{-19}$ cm/molecule (HITRAN). This line is not the strongest available HCl absorption line in the fundamental ν_1 -band of HCl, yet it suffers less from spectral interference by methane as compared to other strong HCl absorption lines [5]. The laser is tuned over the absorption line at a rate of 200 Hz. The laser beam is coupled into a multi-pass cell (Aerodyne, USA) with an effective path length of 76 m (cell volume is 0.5 l) via several silver-coated mirrors and the exiting light is focused using a parabolic mirror on a 2-stage Peltier-cooled detector (PVI-4TE from VIGO, Poland). The pressure in the cell is maintained at 100 mbar using a combination of a pressure controller and a membrane pump. The flow rate through the cell was typically 300 ml/min.

b. HCl reference gas standards

Two different methods were used to prepare HCl reference gas standards in methane at the required amount fractions:

1. Dynamic dilution of a static HCl in CH₄ gas mixture (Figure 1). For the static HCl in CH₄ standard, a commercial mixture was used which had been certified shortly beforehand.

Figure 1 Overview of the experimental set-up used for the dynamic dilution of static HCl in CH₄ and the subsequent measurement by TDLS.

- Dynamic generation based on permeation following ISO 6145-10 and using a magnetic suspension balance (MSB) as shown in Figure 2. For more details on permeation-based system, see Nwaboh et al., 2021. The permeation tube was obtained from Fine Metrology and had a quoted permeation rate of 600 ng/min at 50°C. Part of the flow is directed to the vent while the flow directed to the analyzer is kept constant at 300 ml/min. Note that the permeation chamber itself is flushed with N₂ while the much larger dilution flow is CH₄, therefore there will always be some N₂ in the matrix gas.

Figure 2 Generation of HCl in CH₄ standards based on permeation following ISO 6145-10 (permeation) and ISO 6145-7 (thermal mass flow controllers).

3. HCl results

a. Limit of detection and quantification

The LOD and LOQ were calculated in a similar way as done for ammonia. Here the LOD and LOQ for HCl in CH₄ were determined to be 10 nmol/mol and 33 nmol/mol, respectively.

These values are very similar to those for NH₃ although for HCl a measurement cell with a much longer optical path length (76 m instead of 3 m) was employed. However, the stronger NH₃ absorption (more than twice as strong as HCl for the same amount fraction) and the much stronger spectral interference of CH₄ on the HCl signal as compared to that on the NH₃ signal nullify the benefit of the longer optical path length.

b. Working range

Figure 3 shows a measurement of HCl in methane using dilution of a static mixture with mass flow controllers.

Figure 3 *Measurement of HCl in CH₄. Shown are the measurements at 4 second time resolution (—) and the data averaged over 15 datapoints (—), i.e., 1 minute average.*

For the working range we did not investigate the upper range in of HCl in CH₄ but this has been determined before for HCl in a N₂ matrix. The maximum amount fraction that can be analysed is around 50 µmol/mol above which the HCl absorbance becomes too strong. For a CH₄ matrix this upper range will be slightly lower due to additional absorbance by CH₄ or the other biomethane matrix components. The lower range is given by the limit of quantification. The working range is therefore around 0.03 to 40 µmol/mol.

c. Linearity

The linearity of the system has been tested over the range of 0.6 µmol/mol to 6 µmol/mol according to ISO 6143. The Goodness-of-fit value was 1.01 for a first order linear regression fit. For a satisfactory fit of the data, it was required that the absolute value of the normalized residual was not exceeding 2. The normalized residual is the residual divided by the standard uncertainty. All the normalized residuals were < 2, indicating this function is fit for purpose.

d. Precision

Long-term, continuous measurements were carried of HCl in CH₄ reference gas mixtures generated using the MSB and further also a static HCl in CH₄ mixture was analysed. As an example, Figure 4 shows part of a measurement carried out.

Figure 4 Long-term measurements of HCl generated using the magnetic suspension balance (data are averaged over 15 data points). Around $t=19$ hours the temperature of the permeation chamber was increased leading to an increase in HCl amount fraction. The generated amount fractions takes nearly 3 hours to stabilize (time due to the generation system, not the analyzer).

As an example, at an amount fraction of $12 \mu\text{mol/mol}$, the analyzer response showed peak-to-peak variations up to 6% with a small part of this being due to variations in the generated amount fraction by the MSB. The precision was calculated using the pooled standard deviation as a measure of precision of the method. The resulting precision is $0.05 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ at an HCl amount fraction of $12 \mu\text{mol/mol}$.

e. Measurement uncertainties

As for ammonia, the combined measurement uncertainty of the HCl measurement method was assessed by an empirical approach based upon identification of uncertainty sources as square root of sum of squared quantities of individual sources given in amount fraction units for ammonia measurement.

The uncertainty contributions include the uncertainty of the reference standard, the bias, the precision (the uncertainty due to variation of the matrix gas was not included for HCl). The expanded measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) is 7% relative for measurement of HCl in the lower $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ range. This value increases with decreasing HCl amount fractions. The dominant sources are the uncertainty due to the reference standard and the bias. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable.

f. Response time

The response time both from a low amount fraction of HCl in CH₄ (0.6 μmol/mol) to blank and vice versa were determined (see Figure 3 to get an impression of the analyser time response). Here the t₉₀ value was used as the response time. The determined response times were: T_{90_down} = 50 seconds, T_{90_up} = 8 minutes. The down response time is nearly 10 times faster than the up response time indicating that likely reactions of HCl with the sampling system do occur.

4. Applicability of the protocol to hydrogen fluoride

For hydrogen fluoride (HF), VSL operates a similar TDLS system as used for NH₃ and HCl. A key difference lies however in the used materials as HF reacts with glass-like materials. Examples of such materials are SilcoNert coatings but also the glass chamber of a magnetic suspension balance or the glass tube of the multi-pass cell used for the HCl measurements. It has been shown at VSL that the reaction of HF with such glass materials leads to the formation of SiF₄ (Silicon tetrafluoride) and thus a decrease of the HF amount fraction. Therefore, uncoated mass flow controllers, uncoated pressure controllers and uncoated tubings need to be used (i.e., materials exposed to HF will be mostly stainless steel while tubings can also be polymer-based). For the HF measurement a custom-made Polyacetal cell is used to prevent reactions of HF with the measurement cell. Further, it is advised to keep the system dry.

The TDLS system operated at VSL uses a wavelength of 2475.88 nm (4038.96 cm⁻¹) with a good sensitivity down to the nmol/mol level 0. Figure 5 shows a simulation of the HF absorption in the presence of CH₄ and CO₂. CH₄ is the dominant interfering species while CO₂ interference is minimal. Other gases which might be present in biomethane and for which interference is negligible are H₂O, CO, and HCl while interference for NH₃ is low. Note that for other optical analysers operating at different wavelengths, the levels of interference can be completely different.

Figure 5 *Simulation of the absorption by HF (1 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$) in the presence of CH₄ (80 cmol/mol) and CO₂ (20 cmol/mol) at a pressure of 0.1 bar absolute and temperature of 293 K.*

In general, the protocol will be applicable to HF, but as noted before, the choice of materials requires special attention for the analysis of HF.

5. Conclusions

Within this report the suitability of the protocol developed in A2.1.4 was determined for TDLS analyzers for HCl in biomethane.

Most parts of the protocol are fit for purpose, while some other parts should be more specific. As an example of the latter, the interference testing is not specified in detail. This leaves it more or less open to the user how many interferents and at which level the testing will be done, how it needs to be reported, and what are acceptable levels of interference. Uncertainty contributions due to variations in the biomethane matrix compositions can be large for spectroscopic analyzers, but a full assessment of this uncertainty contribution is a lot of work due to the complexity of the biomethane matrix.

Another point which has already been made in the introduction is that for some compounds like HCl, the EN16723-1:2016 standard does not provide clear limit values but instead refers to CEN/TR 17238:2018. This standard gives an approach for assessment of limit values of contaminants in biomethane based on health assessment criteria, modelling and different scenarios. As a result, when an analyzer for a compound such as HCl has been validated for one country, it may require new validation experiments for other countries with different limit values.

6. References

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